

“THERAPEUTIC AND DIAGNOSTIC ALGORITHM FOR CONGENITAL HYDRONEPHROSIS IN CHILDREN”

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Relevance. Despite the rapid development and implementation of modern high-tech methods, the problem of congenital hydronephrosis (CH) remains relevant and is a relatively common condition of the urinary system. The treatment outcomes for children with congenital hydronephrosis depend on various factors, such as the timing of surgery or obstruction correction, the degree of hydronephrosis, and the child's age. The longer the disease persists, the more pronounced the hydronephrotic changes in the kidneys and the walls of the renal parenchyma, leading to more severe postoperative conditions and a higher likelihood of fatal outcomes.

Objective of the Study. To improve the outcomes of surgical treatment in children with congenital hydronephrosis by optimizing the treatment strategy and the differentiated use of surgical methods.

Materials and Methods. The study is based on the analysis of treatment results of 691 children with congenital hydronephrosis aged 3 to 15 years, treated in the urology departments of three medical institutions in the Ferghana Valley: Andijan Regional Children's Multidisciplinary Medical Center (ARCMCC), Namangan Regional Children's Multidisciplinary Medical Center (NRCMCC), and Ferghana Regional Children's Multidisciplinary Medical Center of Urology from 2013 to 2022.

According to the objective, the patients were divided into two groups for analysis: a comparison group of 337 (48.8%) children treated following standard CH management protocols from 2013 to 2017, and the main group of 354 (51.2%) children treated from 2018 to 2022 using a developed tactical therapeutic-diagnostic algorithm and a modified pyeloplasty method, taking into account the timing of CH development and the possibilities of minimally invasive surgery (laparoscopy).

Among the children included in the study, boys predominated (72.9%) compared to girls (27.1%). The majority of patients (45.1%) were aged 8-15 years (school-age children). In the comparison group, 215 (63.7%) children were admitted in satisfactory condition, 105 (31.1%) in moderate condition, and 17 (5.1%) in severe condition. In the main group, these indicators were 222 (62.7%), 109 (30.8%), and 23 (6.5%), respectively.

Results of the Developed Therapeutic-Tactical Algorithm. The proposed therapeutic-tactical algorithm for managing congenital hydronephrosis in children is based on a multi-positional assessment of the clinical situation and the application of a comprehensive approach to diagnostic and therapeutic tactics, which ensures the maximum potential of qualified and specialized medical care.

According to the proposed algorithm, upon admission of children with congenital hydronephrosis to the emergency department, clinical-anamnestic data were determined (complaints, disease and life history). Special attention was paid to symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, hematuria, or signs of infection, which indicated the onset of renal failure and the presence of concomitant surgical and therapeutic pathologies.

The primary tactical decision for patients with congenital hydronephrosis is to verify complete or partial ureteral obstruction and determine the location of the obstruction using ultrasound or MSCT with excretory urography. To reduce radiation exposure to the child, excretory urography is performed in conjunction with multi-spiral computed tomography, which allows for diagnosis without the need for numerous unnecessary diagnostic tests that are often poorly tolerated by children and parents, potentially leading to refusal of manipulations and surgery altogether.

When diagnosing bilateral hydronephrosis, it is advisable to include additional methods such as general ultrasound and EchoCG to identify accompanying diseases in cases of compensated forms of concurrent therapeutic pathologies. Surgery in these patients is performed in stages, depending on the severity of renal impairment. During this period, measures are taken to reduce renal pressure, administer antibacterial therapy (second-generation cephalosporins, uroseptics, or metronidazole at 500 mg IV, combined with ceftriaxone at 1-2 g IV), antispasmodics, antifungals, and metabolic agents.

Pyeloplasty was considered indicated when hydronephrosis of II-III-IV degree according to the SFU scale was detected. Children aged 6 months to 3 years were recommended lumbar mini-access surgery, from 4 to 7 years transabdominal laparoscopic surgery or lumbar mini-access, and children aged 8 to 15 years predominantly underwent laparoscopic access. For long strictures in the upper third of the ureter, patch pyeloplasty with tension-free anastomosis and minimal de-vascularization of the ureteropelvic junction (UPJ) or pyeloureteral anastomosis according to the clinic's method, with antegrade

stenting of the anastomotic area and drainage of the intervention zone with a Foley catheter for 2 days, was recommended.

Results and Discussion. Based on the deficiencies and shortcomings in the comparison group and the accumulated experience of using minimally invasive surgical methods on the kidney (laparoscopy), the number of laparoscopic approaches increased to 281 (79.3%) children, with conversion to a modified posterior-lateral mini-access in only 1 (0.3% of 281) of them. Among these, 208 (58.7%) were boys and 73 (20.6%) were girls.

The duration of hospital stay after treatment differed significantly. In the comparison group, after 316 (93.7%) traditional open surgeries, the minimum hospitalization period was 12 days, with a maximum of 20-21 days, and the average length of stay was 17.6 days (20.8 ± 3.2 bed days). In the main group, the minimum stay after surgery was 3 days, with a maximum of 6 days, and the average length of stay was 4.5 days (± 0.26). After open surgery with mini-access, the stay was 6.1 ± 0.49 bed days, and after laparoscopic surgery, it was 5.1 ± 0.23 bed days.

Conclusions. The implementation of the developed therapeutic-tactical algorithm for managing children with congenital hydronephrosis, based on a multi-positional assessment of the situation and modern dominant approaches to treating this pathology, allows for improved treatment outcomes in this severe category of patients.

